

Bipolar membrane 3D microlattice electrode assembly design for zero-gap bicarbonate (CO₂) electrolysis

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ABSTRACT

The electrochemical reduction of CO₂ (eCO₂R) from carbon capture solutions, such as (bi)carbonate, offers a promising pathway for energy-efficient carbon recycling compared to traditional gas-phase approaches. However, the development of optimized membrane-electrode designs remains a critical challenge for advancing this technology toward commercial viability. In this study, we present a novel integration of 3D-printed microlattice carbon electrodes with bipolar membranes (BPMs) for bicarbonate electrolysis. We used projection micro-stereolithography (PμSL) to fabricate unique free-standing carbon electrodes with nature-inspired honeycomb architectures. Silver nanoparticles were deposited onto the electrodes via chronoamperometry under varying conditions of deposition potential (-0.1, -0.2, and -0.5 V vs Ag/AgCl), deposition time (0 to 1200 s), and catalyst loading (0 to 0.7 mg/cm²). The optimal BPM-3D electrode assembly significantly enhanced CO production efficiency, achieving a Faradaic efficiency for CO (FE_{CO}) of 38 % - a 22 times increase over uncoated electrodes (1.7 %) - at a current density of 12.5 mA/cm². This configuration, prepared at -0.2 V for 900 s with an Ag loading of 0.5 mg/cm², exhibited improved catalytic activity because of the formation of highly active Ag nanostructures. The electrode demonstrated an Integrated Catalytic Performance Index (ICPI) of approximately 150 mA/Vmg at 50 mA/cm². Stability tests revealed minimal degradation over 14 h of operation, affirming the durability of the Ag-coated 3D electrodes. A preliminary techno-economic analysis projects that CO production costs could be reduced by optimizing Faradaic efficiency (FE) and catalyst loading under scaled conditions. This work lays the foundation for integrating 3D printing and BPM technology for sustainable eCO₂R. However, achieving high selectivity and stability at >100 mA/cm² remains challenging, requiring optimized electrode design and interface engineering for commercial viability.

1. Introduction

Carbon capture and utilization (CCU) is a promising approach for reducing greenhouse gas emissions by conversion and storage of CO₂ into value-added products in a circular pathway. Among the CCU technologies, the electrochemical CO₂ reduction (eCO₂R) to chemicals and fuels presents an important pathway toward establishing a carbon-neutral energy cycle using renewable energy. Significant research has been conducted on eCO₂R to date, including breakthroughs in development of new catalysts and more efficient systems [1–3]. However,

commercial production is still primarily hindered by several challenges: i) the need for high current densities (CD) exceeding 100 mA/cm² and high product selectivities with faradaic efficiencies (FE) approaching 100 % at low cell voltages below 3 V, ii) inefficient CO₂ utilization, and iii) the high capital and energy costs associated with the upstream carbon capture process. In particular, the scientific community, which tends to be highly critical of large-scale deployment, often overlooks the third scenario due to insufficient economic data supporting the advancement of classical methods.

Typical CO₂ electrolyzers are often operated in gas-fed cell designs,

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which are associated with a significant energy penalty of up to 50–175 kJ mol^{-1} required to release pure CO_2 gas from the sorbents used in CO_2 capture processes [4]. In addition, the compression and transport of the CO_2 for utilization are associated with complex engineering and cost requirements for CO_2 electrolyzers. In this regard, investigations on a synergistic coupling between CO_2 capture and CO_2 conversion processes are crucial for improving efficiency and reducing costs. This integrated approach can reduce energy-intensive CO_2 regeneration as well as the need for CO_2 transport and storage, thereby lowering overall operational expenses. By streamlining the electrolysis process and directly utilizing bicarbonate solutions, system design can be simplified and efficiency can be enhanced [5,6].

Direct electrolysis of CO_2 capture solution or bicarbonate (HCO_3^-) solutions emerges as a promising pathway to combine the upstream CO_2 capture process with the downstream CO_2 conversion process to alleviate the energy and cost constraints associated with classical gas-fed CO_2 electrolyzers [5,7–12]. Unlike classical approaches that use either CO_2 gas or CO_2 dissolved in an aqueous medium, the exclusive use of aqueous HCO_3^- offers several advantages: i) a higher maximum carbon concentration in saturated KHCO_3 solution (~ 3.3 M) compared to saturated CO_2 (33 mM), ii) elimination of energy-intensive CO_2 regeneration steps, and iii) no need for pressurization steps. The concept of HCO_3^- electrolysis was demonstrated for the first time by Curtis *et al.* who converted aqueous HCO_3^- directly to CO in Bipolar Membrane (BPM)-based flow cells [5]. The system operates on the principle that the alkaline capture solution is regenerated through the in-situ production of OH^- from water dissociation (WD) at the BPM interface and from eCO_2R at the cathode during electrolysis (Fig. 1) [13–16]. This method is anticipated to significantly reduce both energy consumption and costs compared to classical eCO_2 reduction approaches. However, HCO_3^- electrolysis still faces several challenges in becoming a viable industrial technology. These challenges include a lack of fundamental understanding of the reaction pathways and local mass transfer effects at the membrane (electrolyte)-electrode interface across different reactor designs and the absence of optimally designed high-performance materials including gas diffusion electrodes (GDEs) necessary to achieve the required thresholds towards industrial development.

GDEs have been extensively employed for traditional eCO_2R to achieve stable selectivity and efficiency at high CD. However, such designs are not effective for applications in liquid-fed systems like HCO_3^- electrolyzers. GDEs in liquid-fed bicarbonate electrolyzers must efficiently transport aqueous flows and do not require the hydrophobic properties essential for gas-fed CO_2 electrolyzer electrodes to prevent water accumulation (flooding) [17,18]. Optimal design of GDEs for bicarbonate electrolysis requires precise tailoring of the electrocatalyst

distribution, hydrophobicity, and ion transport characteristics by finely tuning the composition and structure of both the gas diffusion layer and the catalyst layer [7,9,19–25].

Recently, attempts have been made to optimize the electrode architectures by modification of the GDE composition [7] or the use of free-standing porous electrode designs [9]. Among the notable works is the use of an optimized Silver (Ag)-based GDE that reached an FE of up to 82 % at 100 mA/cm^2 for CO from a 3.0 M KHCO_3 solution employing a BPM flow cell [7]. Further advancements include the implementation of porous electrode designs in pressurized systems [9] and the use of cationic surfactants to inhibit the competing hydrogen evolution reaction (HER) [10]. More recently, the correlation of cathode surface pH with C_2 product selectivity has been unraveled [11], and the use of Ni-based single-atom catalysts has been demonstrated to be promising for efficient HCO_3^- electrolysis [8]. However, some challenges still remain, including insufficient performance for large-scale deployment of the electrolyzers and a lack of clarity on how electrode properties, such as surface wettability, influence local CO_2 concentrations at the electrode-membrane interface. In reverse bias HCO_3^- electrolyzer, it is important to note that CO_2 is generated at the BPM-cathode interface, where the H^+ flux is driven out of the interfacial layer of the BPM through the cation exchange layer [5]. Consequently, variations in the hydrophobicity of the electrode surface near the membrane significantly affect the amount of in-situ generated CO_2 that is trapped to form an efficient triple-phase interface [7]. Therefore, a morphology-controlled electrode design is crucial to address these challenges.

3D printing, or additive manufacturing, is rapidly emerging as a transformative technology with immense potential to shape the future of 3D microfabrication, enabling the creation of complex structures with unique physical, chemical and geometrical properties for a wide range of applications [26–29]. This technology allows for the precise incorporation of intricate geometrical features, facilitating the optimization of morphologies - from membrane microstructures to electrode architectures - customized to meet specific application requirements [26,29]. Herein, we introduce new materials design principles to develop novel BPM 3D microlattice electrode assembly (BPM-3D-MEA) for HCO_3^- electrolysis. We report unique 3D microlattice carbon electrodes fabricated by projection micro-stereolithography (PμSL) 3D printing of polymer precursors followed by thermal treatment for application in HCO_3^- electrolysis. To our knowledge, this is the first time such electrodes have been fabricated and applied in HCO_3^- electrolysis. The as-fabricated free-standing carbon electrodes, featuring a nature-inspired honeycomb morphology, were coated with Ag nanoparticles introduced as a catalyst onto the electrode surface through chronoamperometric deposition. The motivation behind the honeycomb

Fig. 1. Bipolar membrane-electrode assembly design for bicarbonate electrolysis using CO_2 capture solutions in a zero-gap flow cell. The BPM supplies H^+ from water dissociation at its interface to the cathode, where the high flux of H^+ reacts with HCO_3^- , producing a high local concentration of CO_2 . This locally generated CO_2 can then be directly utilized for electrochemical reduction, eliminating the need for an external CO_2 supply.

structure design of electrodes is its high surface-to-volume ratio, enabling enhanced electrochemical reaction rates, efficient mass transport, and uniform current distribution. This method ensured precise control over catalyst loadings on the surface of the uniquely structured electrode, enhancing catalyst accessibility and thereby improving electrochemical activity. The resulting electrodes were finally tested in BPM-based HCO_3^- electrolyzers which provide a rigorous environment to assess the electrodes' efficiency and stability. The integration with BPM enables in-situ generation of CO_2 at the membrane-electrode interface to locally produce CO_2 , thereby avoiding the need for external gas supply and energy-intensive regeneration. This innovative approach highlights the potential of the rationally designed 3D microlattice carbon electrodes in advancing electrochemical CO_2 reduction (CO_2R) technologies and pioneering new membrane electrode assembly (MEA) design principles.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Materials

KHCO_3 (99 %), KOH (99 %), AgNO_3 (99 %), KNO_3 (99 %), were purchased from Alfa Aesar (USA). Nafion 117 solution (5 wt %, in a mixture of lower aliphatic alcohols and water) and ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid (EDTA) were purchased from Sigma Aldrich. Nickel foam (>99.99 %) gas diffusion electrode material was purchased from MTI Corporation (USA). Fumasep-FBM BPMs were purchased from Fumatech (Germany) and stored in 0.5 M NaCl solution before use. The properties of these BPMs are provided in Table S1.

2.2. Fabrication of 3D-printed microlattice electrodes

For the fabrication of the 3D polymer precursors, 3D models were designed using Fusion360 software. A reticular electrode structure featuring a nature-inspired honeycomb unit cell with a diameter of 500 μm (Fig S2) was utilized to achieve electrodes with good mechanical properties. The models were printed with a P μ SL 3D printer (MicroArch S140, BMF precision, Boston USA) operating with a wavelength of 405 nm. The employed resin was HTY20 (BMF precision, Boston USA). A schematic of the designed model with dimensions of various aspects, along with a photograph of the electrode after the pyrolysis process, is presented in Fig. S2. The printed polymer precursors were carbonized under an inert atmosphere (500 sccm N_2 flow) in an alumina tube furnace (MTI Corp., GLS 1700x) at 1000 °C for 1 h, effectively preparing them for subsequent Ag deposition. The preparation steps for the 3D Microlattice Electrode are illustrated in Fig. S1.

2.3. Ag electrodeposition

A three-electrode system was used for electrodeposition of Ag nanostructures onto the 3D-printed electrodes from a AgNO_3 solution. The electrolyte solution was prepared by dissolving AgNO_3 to a concentration of 0.01 M in a 0.1 M KNO_3 solution. The deposition process was conducted by chronoamperometry applying a potential in the range of -0.5 V to -1.0 V versus the Ag/AgCl reference electrode, and a counter electrode of Platinum wire as a coil with a length of 10 cm extended wire. The deposition time (from 90 to 1200 s), and the potential (from -0.1 to -0.5 V vs Ag/AgCl) were varied to optimize Ag loading and morphology. A total of 18 electrodes were prepared including the pristine 3D-printed electrodes as shown in Table 1. Finally, a few droplets of 30 % (v/v) Nafion solution were drop-casted onto the electrodes and left to dry to increase the stability of Ag nanostructures on the surface of 3D carbon electrodes. The as-prepared 3D microlattice electrodes were used as cathodes for further analysis. For the anode, the nickel foam was cut into desired dimensions (2×2 cm) with a blade and washed with acetone and water several times before use.

Table 1

The 3D microlattice electrodes prepared at a varying deposition potential and catalyst loading for bicarbonate electrolysis.

Electrodes	V (V) vs Ag/AgCl	t (sec)	Ag loading (mg/cm^2)
E0	–	–	–
E1	-0.1	90	0.1
E2	-0.1	180	0.2
E3	-0.1	300	0.3
E4	-0.1	600	0.4
E5	-0.1	900	0.5
E6	-0.2	90	0.1
E7	-0.2	180	0.2
E8	-0.2	300	0.3
E9	-0.2	600	0.4
E10	-0.2	900	0.5
E11	-0.2	1100	0.6
E12	-0.2	1200	0.7
E13	-0.5	90	0.1
E14	-0.5	180	0.2
E15	-0.5	300	0.3
E16	-0.5	600	0.5
E17	-0.5	900	0.6

2.4. Physical characterization

The morphology of the Ag-coated 3D electrodes was characterized by scanning electron microscopy (SEM, Carl Zeiss NTS GmbH, Germany) in high-vacuum mode with an accelerating voltage of 5–10 kV. The working distance was kept constant around 8–10 mm. X-ray diffraction (XRD) data were collected on a Bruker F8 Focus X-ray diffractometer between 2θ angles of 5° and 90° with a step size of 0.04° and a step time of 0.6 s. X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS; Thermo Scientific Nexsa, USA) was employed for analysis of the elemental composition and chemical states of the as-pyrolyzed 3D carbon and catalyst-decorated electrodes. The XPS spectra were calibrated by $\text{C}1s$ peak located at 284.8 eV. Thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) of the 3D-printed BMF-HTY20 photoresists was performed to identify temperature regions exhibiting onset of degradation and maximum mass loss during the pyrolysis process. Raman spectroscopy was performed using a micro-Raman system (Thermo Scientific Nexsa, USA) with a 532 nm laser wavelength, a $10 \times$ objective, and 8 mW laser power. The data were analysed using OMNIC software (Nicolet Instruments, USA).

2.5. Electrochemical measurements

Electrochemical measurements were conducted at room temperature and pressure using a potentiostat (Biologic with Booster) through two-electrode cell measurements where the working electrode was the cathode. Electrolysis of bicarbonate in a flow cell was performed at constant current densities (chronopotentiometry) between 12.5 and 100 mA/cm^2 in a two-electrode flow cell system. Before electrolysis, linear sweep voltammetry (LSV) measurements were recorded at a scan rate of 100 mV/s in the cell voltage range of 0 to -6 V to see the I-V characteristics of the flow cell.

2.6. Electrolytic flow cell measurements

An electrochemical flow cell supplied by Electrocell (Denmark), equipped with bipolar membranes (Fumatech, Germany) was modified to a zero-gap cell and used to test the micro-fabricated electrodes in 3 M KHCO_3 electrolyte. This flow plate design is similar to a previously reported design for a CO_2 electrolyzer [3]. The flow cell consisted of housing, gaskets, anode and cathode flow-field plates and a MEA. The scheme of the zero-gap flow cell equipped with BPM - 3D microlattice electrode assembly design is shown in Fig. S3. The internal housing was made from polytetrafluoroethylene (PTFE) material serving to deliver liquid electrolytes to the anode and cathode. All gaskets were cut from 1.5 mm thick chemical-resistant compressible PTFE. The PTFE gaskets

are chemically inert to cathode and anode feeds and are highly compressible, ensuring both liquid and gas-tight seals. The 4 cm² MEA was sandwiched between a Ti cathode flow plate and a stainless steel anode flow plate, for their inherent chemical stabilities in basic and acidic conditions, and inactivity towards the OER and CO₂R reaction. The flow plates featured serpentine channels that were 1.5 mm wide and 1.5 mm deep, separated by 1-mm ribs. The MEA consisted of a Ni foam anode (2 × 2 cm²), a BPM (2.5 × 2.5 cm²), and an Ag-coated 3D-printed electrodes as the cathode (2 × 2 cm²). Si layer with a window of 2 × 2 cm² was sandwiched between the BPM and the Ag-coated 3D-printed electrodes to mask the inactive area of the cathode. The entire assembly was sandwiched between two stainless steel housings with 8 bolts of 6.35 mm diameter tightened to a torque of 2 Nm.

The catholyte solution of the flow cell was composed of 3.0 M KHCO₃ solution which was recirculated at 50 mL min⁻¹ for the duration of all experiments using a peristaltic pump (McMaster-Carr; 43205K11). EDTA was added to the 3.0 M KHCO₃ at a concentration of 0.02 M for all experiments to prevent electrodeposition of electrolyte impurities on the GDE surface [3]. The anode electrolyte was 1.0 M KOH solution delivered by a peristaltic pump at a flow rate of 50 mL/min. N₂ (Praxair, 99.9 %) was continuously purging the headspace of the catholyte reservoir (250 mL round bottom flask) at 50 sccm to carry electrolysis products from the catholyte to the gas chromatograph (GC; SRI-8610C; Mandel). A schematic of the experimental setup for the continuous bicarbonate electrolysis is presented in Fig. S4.

2.7. Product quantification

First, the GC was calibrated by injecting different calibration gas mixes from NorLAB containing CO, CH₄, H₂, C₂H₄, C₂H₆, CO₂, and C₃H₈ at concentrations ranging from 100 - 50,000 ppm. The GC was equipped with a packed MolSieve 5A column and a packed HayeSepD column. Helium (Praxair, 99.999 %) was used as the carrier gas. Two thermal conductivity detectors (TCD) were used, one to quantify H₂ concentrations and the other for CO concentrations. To ensure that the products were quantified after the saturation of the catholyte, data were collected every 20 min for a time interval of 1 h.

2.8. Performance evaluation

The Faradaic efficiency (FE) of the product can be calculated according to the below equation:

$$FE(\%) = \frac{Q_{\text{product}}}{Q_{\text{total}}} \times 100\% \quad (1)$$

where Q_{product} and Q_{total} are charges transferred for product formation and charge passed through the working electrode, respectively.

Based on the above equation, the detailed calculation for FE of gas product could be written as:

$$FE(\%) = \frac{n \times C_{\text{product}} \times \varnothing t \times \frac{P_0}{RT} \times F}{I \times t} \times 100\% \quad (2)$$

where C_{product} and n are the concentration of gas product measured by GC and the number of electrons required for producing one molecule of the related gas product, respectively. \varnothing is gas flow rate, t is the electrolysis time, P_0 is ambient pressure, F is Faraday constant, R is ideal gas constant, T is absolute temperature, and I is current.

To compare the performance of the 3D printed electrodes for electrochemical CO₂ reduction while considering multiple factors, a new parameter called the "Integrated Catalyst Performance Index (ICPI)" is defined. This parameter would combine FE, current density (J), electrode deposition potential (V_d), and catalyst loading (C_L) into a single metric. The ICPI was defined as:

$$ICPI = \frac{(FE * J)}{(|V_d| * C_L)} \quad (3)$$

The ICPI serves as a holistic descriptor integrating both catalytic performance and fabrication cost-efficiency. It is introduced to evaluate the overall effectiveness of electrocatalysts for CO₂ reduction, moving beyond isolated metrics such as J or FE. The ICPI incorporates these key performance indicators to offer a more comprehensive measure of both catalytic activity and energetic input during catalyst synthesis. The deposition potential is included in the denominator (as its absolute value) to reflect the energetic demand of the electrodeposition process. A more negative deposition potential implies greater energy consumption during synthesis. By penalizing such cases, ICPI promotes not only high-performance but also energy-efficient catalyst production. A higher ICPI would indicate better overall performance, considering both the electrode preparation and its catalytic activity. This aligns with broader goals of economic viability and sustainable materials design. Moreover, the inclusion of $|V_n|$ indirectly captures the trade-off between finely structured morphologies, often formed at higher energetic costs, and practical synthesis constraints. While not a direct energy cost in operation, $|V_n|$ reflects the intensity of resources used during fabrication.

2.9. Preliminary techno-economic analysis

The preliminary techno-economic analysis of CO production via bicarbonate electrolysis focused primarily on operational expenditures, excluding capital costs to better reflect the performance-based parameters from lab-scale data. The cost analysis incorporated key operational parameters including electricity consumption, catalyst utilization, and feedstock costs. Calculations were performed based on the present lab-scale setup with varying operating conditions: cell voltage (3.5–5.6 V), current densities (12.5–100 mA/cm²), and catalyst loadings (low mg/cm² 0.1 and high 0.6 mg/cm²). The analysis accounted for the costs associated with electricity consumption, catalyst materials, and KHCO₃ feedstock sourced from a direct air capture system based on pre-set baseline parameters. The detailed baseline parameters, cost equations, and electrochemical reactions are provided in Table S2. The total CO production cost was calculated by combining energy input, FE, and material costs.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Physical characterization

The 3D model of the fabricated electrodes (Fig. 2a) with a honeycomb mesh structure, featuring precisely engineered geometric dimensions (Fig. 2b), ensured structural stability and high porosity, which are essential for enhanced electrochemical performance. After undergoing the pyrolysis process, the polymeric structures are successfully converted into conductive microlattice carbon while maintaining their original architecture (Fig. 2c). The TGA curve (Fig. S5) shows the thermal decomposition of the 3D-printed carbon electrodes during carbonization. The sample remains stable up to 300 °C, with only 5 % weight loss from 200 - 300 °C mainly due to moisture evaporation. The main decomposition occurs between 350 - 450 °C, with an 85 % mass loss as the polymer structure breaks down. Above 500 °C, the mass stabilizes at 8 - 10 % of the initial weight, indicating complete conversion to a carbon structure suitable for Ag deposition. This transformation highlighted the robustness and adaptability of the fabrication process for advanced electrode applications.

The use of an electrochemical deposition method allowed for a facile and effective strategy for coating catalysts onto the electrodes with controlled morphology by forming nanostructures. Fig. 2a-d shows the digital photographs of the Ag-coated electrodes whereas Fig. 2e-h shows SEM images of pristine and Ag-coated 3D microlattice carbon electrodes

Fig. 2. Characterization of Ag-coated 3D microlattice carbon electrodes obtained by 3D-printing. a) 3D model of microlattice carbon electrodes with honeycomb mesh structure. b) Structural dimensions indicating specific geometric features of the electrode architecture. Digital photographs of the 3D-printed microlattice carbon electrodes c) after the pyrolysis process and d) after Ag electrodeposition. (e-f) SEM images of bare/pristine 3D printed microlattice carbon electrodes at different magnifications, showing the honeycomb structure. (g-h) SEM images of Ag-coated electrodes, revealing leaf-like Ag growth on the carbon surface. (i-j) SEM images of Ag-coated electrodes before electrolysis at different magnifications, showing the initial Ag nanostructure distribution. (k-l) SEM images of Ag-coated electrodes after electrolysis of 14 h, demonstrating morphological changes in the Ag coating. (m) TEM image of the Ag-coated microlattice carbon structure [1]. (n) Raman spectrum of the Ag-coated electrode, indicating characteristic peaks of microlattice carbon and possible SERS effects from Ag. (o) XRD patterns of the Ag-coated electrodes before and after electrolysis, showing crystalline structure changes due to bicarbonate/CO₂ electroreduction.

fabricated by PμSL 3D printing. The pristine electrodes (Fig. 2e-f) exhibit a highly ordered honeycomb structure with hexagonal cells with 200 μm in diameter, characterized by smooth surfaces, sharp edges, and a well-defined hexagonal lattice structure with clean and uniform surfaces. The structural features of the 3D microlattice carbon electrodes are significantly smaller and more well-defined than what has been achieved by similar methods using stereolithography-based 3D printing and pyrolysis [29,30]. The Ag-coated electrodes (Fig. 2g-h) display a rough, highly textured surface due to distinctive leaf-like structures on the micrometer scale, which uniformly cover the external electrode surface as well as the internal surface (Fig S6), while preserving its 3D architecture. This leaf-like morphology, characterized by extended, overlapping, and branched formations, includes characteristic leaf-like rod structures in tree-like fractal patterns of electrodeposited Ag nanoparticles [31]. These structures can range up to several tens of micrometers in size, with finer features reaching down to a few tens of nanometers. This results in

a significant increase in the electrochemically active surface area compared to smoother surfaces and a high availability of catalytic sites for CO₂ reduction [32]. The hierarchical structure combines the macro-porosity of the 3D-printed framework with micro- and nano-scale features of the Ag coating, potentially offering a balance between high surface area and efficient mass transport. Compared to smoother or more compact Ag morphologies, the leaf-like structure minimizes charge transfer resistance and enhances selectivity toward CO production. However, variations in the density and size of these leaf-like structures across the surface may lead to some heterogeneity in catalytic performance, warranting further investigation into deposition parameters for optimal uniformity and performance.

Fig. 2i-l reveals the morphological changes in the Ag-coated 3D printed electrodes before and after bicarbonate electrolysis. Initially, the Ag catalyst exhibits a complex, high surface area with intricate leaf-like branching patterns (Fig. 2i-j). After electrolysis of 14 h, the leaf-like

structure transitions into more compact, rod-shaped, or elongated prismatic particles with more defined edges (Fig. 2k-l). These restructured particles are smaller (sub-micron to a few micrometers in length) and more evenly distributed, albeit with lower overall density. Notably, some agglomeration is observed, where clusters of rod-like particles have coalesced, particularly visible in the higher magnification image (1 μm scale bar), which is also supported by the XPS data obtained before and after electrolysis (Fig. S6). XPS analysis reveals that initially, the electrode is primarily composed of metallic Ag (Ag^0), as indicated by its characteristic peaks. After electrolysis, new signals corresponding to Ag oxide (Ag_2O) and Ag carbonate (Ag_2CO_3) appear, showing that a large portion of the surface has reacted. The composition shifts dramatically, with Ag_2CO_3 making up 58.3 %, Ag_2O at 26.8 %, and only 14.9 % of metallic Ag remaining. The oxygen spectrum further supports this transformation, confirming the oxidation and carbonation of the surface. This morphological evolution, consistent with electrochemical restructuring processes reported in the literature [33–35], suggests significant dissolution, redeposition, and aggregation of Ag during electrolysis. Yun *et al.* investigated the Ag nanoparticle degradation during CO_2 electrolysis for CO production, observing a 10 % decrease in activity for operations over 12 h [34]. This was attributed to the formation of small particles (<5 nm) on the carbon support, which agglomerate into larger, multi-domain structures over time, deviating from the original active sites and reducing CO production efficiency. Thus, the transition from high-surface-area leaf-like structures to more compact, partially agglomerated rod-like particles likely results in a decrease in overall catalytic surface area, potentially impacting catalytic activity and efficiency. These observations underscore the dynamic nature of the Ag catalyst under operational conditions and highlight the importance of considering catalyst restructuring and agglomeration in optimizing electrocatalysts for long-term stability and performance in bicarbonate electrolysis applications. Indeed, various strategies can be developed to enhance stability during the CO_2R reaction, such as employing lipid ligands bound on the surface of Ag to prevent its agglomeration as proved by TEM images of Ag nanoparticles after 50 h of CO_2 electrolysis (Fig. 2m) [33], thereby contributing to its overall stability.

Further characterization of the Ag-coated 3D-printed electrodes was performed by recording the Raman spectrum (Fig. 2n). The spectrum shows characteristic peaks that align well with microlattice carbon structures. The most prominent feature is a large, sharp peak around 1580 cm^{-1} , which can be attributed to the G-band (graphite band) of microlattice carbon, representing in-plane vibrations of sp^2 bonded carbon atoms. The peak near 1350 cm^{-1} corresponds to the d-band (disorder band), indicating the presence of defects or disorder in the carbon structure, which is common in microlattice carbon [30,36]. The broad peak in the $2500\text{--}3000\text{ cm}^{-1}$ region is likely the 2D or G-band, a second-order overtone of the d-band, characteristic of graphitic materials including microlattice carbon.

The structural evolution observed in the XRD patterns provides valuable insights into the electrode transformation during the electrocatalytic process, which is essential for understanding its performance, stability, and potential for optimization of bicarbonate electrolysis. The patterns for Ag-coated 3D printed electrodes before and after electrolysis of bicarbonate are presented in Fig. 2o. Significant structural changes in the electrode material due to this electrochemical process were observed. Before electrolysis, the pattern shows broader, less defined peaks, characteristic of the more amorphous structure of microlattice carbon with some crystalline Ag present. Sharp peaks at around 38° , 44° , and 64° 2θ indicate crystalline Ag, corresponding to the (111), (200), and (220) planes, verifying the successful Ag coating. A broad peak near 26° suggests the presence of amorphous or graphitic carbon. Additionally, some peaks may represent the formation of Ag carbonate or other Ag compounds due to interactions with the electrolyte or reaction intermediates. After electrolysis, the Ag peaks remain visible, but changes in peak intensity and shifts suggest structural alterations due to the

electrochemical process. There was a marked increase in the number and intensity of sharp peaks, particularly in the $20 - 40^\circ$ 2θ range. The sharper peaks likely indicate the growth and restructuring of Ag crystals, which play a crucial role as catalysts in CO_2 /bicarbonate reduction to CO. These observations indicate potential modifications in crystallinity or particle size of Ag, possibly due to surface interactions or restructuring during CO production. This analysis highlights the structural stability of the electrode and confirms successful catalyst deposition.

3.2. Electrochemical characterization

Before CO_2 electrolysis, the LSV curves were recorded in a two-electrode zero-gap flow cell over a cell potential in the range of 0 to -6 V, to depict the electrochemical behavior of various Ag-coated electrodes subjected to different deposition time (0–900 s) and electrodeposition potentials (-0.1 V vs Ag/AgCl, -0.2 V vs Ag/AgCl and -0.5 V vs Ag/AgCl). Across all deposition potentials, increased deposition time generally led to higher current densities, indicating enhanced electrocatalytic activity, likely due to increased Ag loading and optimized nanoparticle distribution. Most electrodes exhibit onset potentials of around -2.6 V (Fig. 3-c), indicating the initiation of the CO_2 reduction reaction, coherent to the work of Berliquette *et al.* who also recorded a similar onset potential in a 3 M bicarbonate solution with Ag-coated carbon cathodes [5]. Electrodes prepared at lower potentials (-0.1 V vs Ag/AgCl) (Fig. 3a) and higher potentials (-0.5 V vs Ag/AgCl) (Fig. 3c) generally show higher onset potentials and lower current densities (shallower slopes) which could be attributed to the formation of larger, less active Ag particles. It is also evident that the pristine electrode shows the highest onset potential with poor catalytic activity. Notably, electrodes prepared at -0.2 V vs Ag/AgCl exhibit the steepest LSV slopes and highest current densities, particularly at 900 s deposition time reaching up to 84 mA/cm^2 at -4.5 V, compared to electrodes prepared at -0.2 V vs Ag/AgCl and -0.5 V vs Ag/AgCl reaching 80 mA/cm^2 and 77 mA/cm^2 , respectively. This indicates the optimal catalytic performance at -0.2 V vs Ag/AgCl and 900 s deposition time, aligning with previous findings where moderate deposition potentials yielded superior CO_2 reduction activity due to favorable Ag nanostructure formation [37,38]. The less pronounced performance enhancement observed for -0.5 V deposition potential may be attributed to the agglomeration of Ag particles at more negative potentials, reducing active surface area and hence the efficiency of CO_2 electrolysis [38]. Moreover, electrodes coated at -0.2 V and -0.5 V, 900 s deposition time i.e. E10 (Fig. 3b) and E17 (Fig. 3c), respectively, resulted in the lowest onset potential. E10 also drives a high current density of 100 mA/cm^2 at the lowest potential ($\sim 4.7\text{ V}$) similar to that of E4 of 100 mA/cm^2 . However, at this same potential, E17 drives a lower current density ($\sim 90\text{ mA/cm}^2$) compared to the other electrodes with higher Ag loading ($> 0.5\text{ mg/cm}^2$) coated at different potentials. This can be attributed to the surface morphology, over-agglomeration or crystalline structure of Ag coating of E17. For instance, rough Ag surfaces can enhance the adsorption of CO_2 which can lead to a reduction in onset potential and increased current density, which is limiting phenomenon in the case of E17. In general, electrodes coated with Ag at moderate potentials like E10 (Fig. 3b) exhibit lower onset potentials and drive higher current densities which is crucial for efficient CO_2 reduction via bicarbonate electrolysis. This is likely due to the formation of finer, more active Ag nanoparticles. This is supported by the SEM images showing a more dendritic or rough surface morphology (Fig. 2h), which typically enhances catalytic activity by providing more active sites for the CO_2 reduction reaction compared to smooth morphologies [39–42].

3.3. Flow cell bicarbonate electrolysis tests

The electrolytic reduction of CO_2 to CO was performed in a 3.0 M $\text{KHCO}_3(\text{aq})$ solution to elucidate the performance of the 3D-printed electrode sets within a current density range of $12\text{--}100\text{ mA/cm}^2$. All

Fig. 3. The LSV curves in a 2-electrode electrolyzer set-up recorded during electrolysis of 3 M bicarbonate solution for Ag-coated electrodes prepared at variable deposition times and electrode potentials of a) -0.1 V b) -0.2 V and c) -0.5 V vs Ag/AgCl.

Ag-coated electrodes displayed a higher FE_{CO} compared to the pristine electrodes complying with the catalytic effect of Ag nanostructures. In general, the results from the GC analysis show a reduced FE_{CO} as the current density increased which was attributed to the dominance of the HER as shown in Fig. 4a-c, reaching up to 90 % for electrodes coated at -0.5 V. The declining FE_{CO} with increasing current density aligns well with previous studies on Ag-based catalysts [5,7]. As current density increases, mass transport limitations become more pronounced, resulting in CO_2 depletion near the electrode surface and increasing competition from HER. This results in a lower availability of CO_2 for reduction, thereby reducing the efficiency of CO production. It is well-noted that while high current densities can increase overall reaction rates, they often lead to lower selectivity for CO_2 due to mass transfer limitations and increased local pH shifts [43,44]. One strategy to suppress HER involves innovative catalyst designs, such as the use of oxide-encapsulated Ag catalysts, which mitigate bicarbonate-driven HER and enhance CO selectivity, thereby improving the stability of bicarbonate electrolysis systems [45].

The catalyst loading, controlled by electrodeposition time, exhibited a significant influence on the FE during bicarbonate electrolysis, with distinct optimal conditions emerging at different deposition potentials.

Among the electrodes coated at -0.1 V, a maximum FE_{CO} of 20 % was recorded at Ag loading of 0.4 mg/cm² (E4, Fig. 4a) corresponding to a deposition time of 600 s at a current of 12.5 mA/cm². The maximum FE_{CO} achieved at an Ag loading of 0.4 mg/cm² marks the optimal condition, with a decline observed at higher deposition times (900 s) or increased Ag loading (0.5 mg/cm²). A similar behavior with a local maximum FE_{CO} for a specific catalyst loading was also observed for deposition at higher potentials (Fig. 4e-f). The reduction of FE_{CO} at excessive loading can be due to agglomeration of catalyst particles, reducing the effective surface area and thereby decreasing the efficiency. Moreover, excessive catalyst loading can increase the electrical resistance of the electrode, leading to an overall decrease in efficiency. The E10 electrode, coated at -0.2 V vs. Ag/AgCl, exhibited the highest FE_{CO} of 37.3 % of all electrodes at 12.5 mA/cm² and 900 s of deposition time. This high FE_{CO} was achieved at a high loading of 0.5 mg/cm² (Fig. 4e), apparently providing the most active sites for the reaction to occur as compared to the other electrodes. A study by Lees *et al.* on Ag-coated GDE/hybrid samples for bicarbonate electrolysis revealed a 26 % increase in FE_{CO} i.e. from 65 ± 2 % for pristine electrodes to 82 ± 2 % at an optimal Ag loading of 1.3 mg/cm² [7]. Although our study reports a lower FE_{CO} (37.3 %), we used a scalable, waste-minimized 3D printing

Fig. 4. CO and H₂ FE measured at 12 - 100 mA cm⁻² current densities in 3.0 M KHCO₃ solution for Ag-based electrodes coated at a) -0.1 V b) -0.2 V c) -0.5 vs Ag/AgCl. Variation of the CO FE vs catalyst loading at 12.5 and 100 mA cm⁻² current densities in 3.0 M KHCO₃ solution for Ag-based electrodes coated at d) -0.1 V e) -0.2 V f) -0.5 vs Ag/AgCl.

method with a Ag-catalyst loading of 0.5 mg/cm^2 , improving material efficiency and sustainability. Given that high catalyst loadings are economically unfavorable, it is essential to explore alternative strategies for reducing material usage without sacrificing performance. For example, Wu *et al.* employed flame spray pyrolysis for Ag deposition over carbon cloth which enabled a threefold reduction in Ag loading - from 0.9 to 0.3 mg/cm^2 - while still achieving over 55 % FE_{CO} at 100 mA/cm^2 [46]. It is apparent that in classical GDE architectures, a thicker catalyst layer enhances mass transport by maintaining efficient gas diffusion pathways, improving CO_2 access to active sites, and increasing FE for CO production. The differing catalyst loading trends between 3D microlattice carbon electrodes and GDEs may stem from variations in porosity, gas diffusion, and wettability, affecting CO_2 transport and active site utilization. Further investigation is needed to quantify these effects on FE and overall catalytic performance.

For electrodes coated at -0.5 V , an optimal FE_{CO} of 28.4 % was obtained at Ag loading of 0.1 mg/cm^2 corresponding to a deposition time of 90 s. Notably, this electrode exhibited a higher optimal FE_{CO} compared to the best-performing electrode prepared a low deposition potential (Fig. 4d), despite its lower Ag loading (Fig. 4f). This indicates that the Ag deposition potential plays a critical role in determining the morphology and distribution of the catalyst on the electrode surface, which in turn has a direct impact on the efficiency of CO_2 reduction. Appropriate electrodeposition potentials can enhance the electronic properties of the catalyst, facilitating better electron transfer during the reduction process. Furthermore, variations in deposition potential can lead to differences in the size, shape, and uniformity of the Ag nanoparticles, as well as their distribution across the electrode. These morphological characteristics influence the number of active sites available for catalysis, the accessibility of CO_2 molecules to these sites, and the overall selectivity of the CO_2 reduction reaction towards CO production. As a result, optimizing the deposition potential is essential for achieving a catalyst surface that maximizes the FE for CO while minimizing the required catalyst loading.

Fig. 5a-f shows the variation in FE with Ag deposition potential across different current densities revealing a distinct trend, wherein optimal deposition potentials enhance CO_2 reduction selectivity, while

excessively negative potentials compromise performance. It was pointed out earlier that the optimal performance in CO_2 electroreduction (FE_{CO} of 37.3 %) was achieved at moderately negative deposition potentials (-0.2 V vs Ag/AgCl) combined with lower current densities (12.5 mA/cm^2). This trend can be attributed to the formation of a higher density of active Ag sites at moderate deposition potentials, striking a balance between sufficient Ag coverage and an optimal particle size distribution. Moderate Ag nucleation and growth conditions promote the formation of more active sites for the CO_2 reduction reaction, aligning with previous findings [47]. In fact, at optimal deposition potential, the adsorption of CO_2 and subsequent electron transfer on the Ag surface is enhanced, leading to higher CO production and reduced competition from the HER [48]. However, the observed decrease in FE_{CO} at more negative potential (-0.5 V Ag/AgCl) is likely due to suboptimal surface morphology or agglomeration effects, resulting in poor adhesion of the catalyst to the substrate, which leads to a decreased stability and efficiency over time. The negative impact of high deposition potentials on the catalytic effect during CO_2 electrolysis is more prominent at low current densities. At lower current densities, the reaction kinetics are slower, and the influence of catalyst structure and surface properties, which are directly affected by high deposition potentials, becomes more critical. Conversely, at higher current densities, mass transport limitations and other factors like CO_2 depletion near the electrode surface tend to dominate the reaction environment. While the structural issues caused by high deposition potentials still exist, their relative impact on overall performance may be less noticeable because the rate of CO_2 reduction is more constrained by mass transport and diffusion limitations than by the microstructure of the catalyst [49,50].

Overall, optimizing both the Ag deposition potential and current density is crucial for achieving maximum FE_{CO} . While a few previous studies have shown that optimizing potential alone can enhance CO selectivity, it is clear that this must be coupled with careful control of current density to avoid the negative impacts of mass transport limitations [51]. Our findings are in line with these observations, further reinforcing the need for a balanced approach in optimizing CO_2 electroreduction systems for maximum CO production efficiency.

Fig. 5. The impact of Ag deposition potential on the FE_{CO} during CO_2 electrolysis at five different current densities: a) 12.5 mA/cm^2 , b) 25 mA/cm^2 , c) 50 mA/cm^2 , d) 75 mA/cm^2 , e) 100 mA/cm^2 . The deposition time was 900 s. The catalyst loading (0.5 mg/cm^2) was same for all except for the potential at -0.5 V which was 0.6 mg/cm^2 . f) Comparison of the maximum FE_{CO} achieved in this work with values reported in selected literature.

3.3.1. Strategies to improve selectivity

While this first demonstration focused on establishing the feasibility of integrating a microlattice structure with a bipolar membrane, future optimization will target improvements in FE, among others. The development of catalysts with high activity under acidic conditions, alongside systems capable of efficiently converting OH^- , generated during CO_2 reduction (CO_2RR) and/or the hydrogen evolution reaction (HER), back into reactive carbon species, is critically important. Promising strategies include conformal coating of the microlattice with CO -selective innovative catalysts based on Ag-based alloys, and geometrical tuning of the lattice to enhance mass transport, buffer capacity, and reactant accessibility. Exploring new catalyst compositions, such as oxide-encapsulated Ag catalysts or bimetallic materials [52], that offer superior selectivity towards CO production is essential. The use of single-atom catalysts, such as Ni-based systems, in combination with bicarbonate electrolytes, presents a compelling approach for enhancing the efficiency of bicarbonate electrolysis [8]. Moreover, surface modifications to control wettability, such as introducing hydrophobic domains, could also help maintain a stable gas-liquid-solid interface and reduce flooding.

Further enhancement may be achieved by co-optimizing the microlattice with a tailored BPM to improve local CO_2 regeneration via water dissociation and proton delivery. For instance, incorporating highly active water dissociation catalysts at the BPM interface, combined with ultrathin, porous ion-exchange layers, can significantly reduce voltage losses and enhance water transport under high current densities. Surface modification of cation exchange membranes with tailored ionomers has recently been reported to result in enhanced bicarbonate electrolysis performance, including reduced cell - voltage, improved local pH control, and increased Faradaic efficiency for formate production [53]. Additionally, engineering of flow field designs and electrolyte flow rates can minimize concentration gradients and promote uniform reaction conditions. Moreover, investigating the impact of electrolyte composition, additives, and flow dynamics to optimize local CO_2 concentration and pH at the electrode-electrolyte interface. These integrated strategies, grounded in recent advances in flow-cell and electrocatalyst design, will guide our ongoing efforts to scale up and optimize the performance of this novel electrode platform.

3.4. Integrated catalyst performance index

To identify the optimal electrodes under the constraint of various operating parameters, the ICPI was evaluated across a range of current densities from 12.5 to 100 mA/cm^2 for three electrode types (E4, E10, and E13) that provide the highest FE_{CO} for each deposition potential (Fig. 6). As illustrated in Fig. 6, E13 demonstrated the highest ICPI value among all tested electrodes, reaching approximately 150 mA/Vmg at 75 mA/cm^2 , indicating its superior catalytic efficiency under these conditions. Electrodes deposited at -0.5 V vs Ag/AgCl (EC series) exhibit superior ICPI values, especially at 50 mA/cm^2 , as higher deposition potentials improve catalytic activity by enhancing surface interaction and reducing overpotential [48]. Conversely, excessive catalyst loading, as seen with electrodes like E4 and E10, often results in diminished ICPI, since increased catalyst quantity beyond an optimal loading threshold does not proportionally enhance performance and can lead to inefficiencies [54]. Additionally, while ICPI generally increases with current density, extreme densities (e.g. 100 mA/cm^2) can decrease ICPI, likely due to mass transport limitations and increased energy losses. Therefore, achieving the highest ICPI is best realized with electrodes featuring high deposition potentials and minimal catalyst loadings at moderate current densities, reflecting a balance between efficient catalytic material use and optimal operational conditions.

Porous carbon-based electrodes like carbon cloth and gas diffusion electrodes (GDEs) are typically essential components in modern electrolysis, bridging the gap between traditional and advanced electrode technologies. These materials have been effectively employed for bicarbonate electrolysis to date. For instance, Li *et al.* used carbon cloth (Ag loading of 100 - 120 counts per second by X-ray fluorescence) combined with a BPM for bicarbonate electrolysis in a zero-gap electrochemical cell. A FE of up to 79 % was achieved in a CO_2 -saturated 3.0 M KHCO_3 solution at a current density of 25 mA/cm^2 , decreasing to approximately 35 % at 100 mA/cm^2 [5]. These results demonstrate a FE exceeding that of the present study by more than threefold. At this stage, despite the lower FE we report compared to previous works on bicarbonate electrolysis (Fig. 5f), we believe our work complements such studies by introducing a morphology-controlled 3D microlattice electrode design with some added benefits. 3D printing provides flexibility

Fig. 6. ICPI values for electrodes E4, E10, and E13, representing the highest FE_{CO} performers at -0.1 V, -0.2 V, and -0.5 V deposition potentials, respectively, plotted over a range of current densities. The ICPI peaks at ~ 150 mA/Vmg for E13 at 75 mA/cm^2 .

to design more complex and highly customized geometries, with the potential to enhance performance through increased surface area or improved mass transport, creating opportunities for further analysis and development. Additionally, the PTFE-free, fully carbon-based composition of the 3D microlattice electrodes not only reduces material costs but also enhances sustainability, particularly when combined with bipolar membrane (BPM) integration, which improves energy efficiency and CO₂ utilization (Table 2). Moreover, the design principles presented in this study can be leveraged to further optimize GDEs for bicarbonate electrolysis, opening pathways for the development of next-generation electrode architectures. Building on these findings, our future work will focus on exploring various 3D-printed electrode architectures, alongside optimizing catalyst coating and morphology, to develop high-performance, scalable membrane-electrode assemblies tailored for efficient CO₂ electroreduction.

3.5. Stability tests during bicarbonate electrolysis

The stability of a bicarbonate electrolyzer equipped with BPM-3D-EA assembly for CO₂ electrolysis was investigated under various deposition

Table 2

Comparison of the 3D Microlattice Carbon Electrode with State-of-the-Art Gas Diffusion and Metal-Based Electrodes in the Context of Green Chemistry Principles. The energy efficiency and CO₂ utilization efficiency are the key system-level advantages gained by the integration of the present electrodes with BPMs.

Green chemistry principle	This Study (3D Microlattice Carbon Electrodes)	State-of-the-Art (Gas Diffusion and/or Metal-Based Electrodes)	Ref.
Manufacturing approach	Utilizes additive manufacturing (3D printing), reducing material waste	Conventional gas diffusion electrodes (GDEs) require multi-step fabrication processes, including hydrophobic treatments, contributing to material waste and inefficiencies	[59, 60]
Precision and Performance Enhancement	Allows precise electrode design for optimized gas-liquid interface and reactant transport	GDEs typically have less design flexibility and may exhibit heterogeneous porosity and non-uniform reactant distribution	[43, 61]
Environmental and chemical safety	Free from polytetrafluoroethylene (PTFE), eliminating degradation risks associated with perfluorosulfonic acid (PFAS)	PTFE-containing electrodes can degrade into environmentally persistent PFAS	[7, 62]
Material cost	Purely carbon-based material reduces electrode costs, making the approach more economically viable	Metal-based electrodes, especially those incorporating platinum-group metals, are expensive.	[2, 61]
Energy* efficiency	Lower energy input due to bipolar membrane (BPM) integration, eliminating the need for CO ₂ gas. Direct bicarbonate electrolysis reduces the need for CO ₂ compression and transport.	Gas-phase CO ₂ electrolysis requires additional energy-intensive CO ₂ regeneration steps.	[60, 63]
CO ₂ utilization efficiency*	BPM-based electrode system minimizes CO ₂ loss, enhancing overall process efficiency	Gas-phase CO ₂ electrolysis often suffers from significant CO ₂ losses due to inefficient mass transport, necessitating high-pressure systems.	[64]

conditions, with voltage monitored over 14 h at a constant current density of 100 mA/cm². Fig. 7 illustrates results from the stability study showing distinct trends based on deposition potential and time. The general trend shows that electrodes deposited at more negative potentials (−0.2 V and −0.5 V) and for longer durations (600 s and 900 s) exhibit higher and more stable operating voltages, indicating increased resistance or possibly a more significant overpotential required for CO₂ reduction. This can be attributed to excessive Ag deposition leading to thicker, less uniform coatings that may hinder effective electron transfer and gas diffusion [55,56]. Electrodes deposited at −0.2 V exhibited the highest initial voltages, particularly for shorter deposition time of 300 s, suggesting a more active surface for CO₂ reduction. While longer deposition times at −0.2 V yielded lower, more stable operating voltages due to uniform catalyst distribution, electrodes prepared at −0.5 V exhibited initial low overpotential but showed increased voltage instability - likely caused by agglomeration and restructuring of Ag nanoparticles under operational stress. The −0.5 V deposition condition resulted in intermediate performance, with a slight upward voltage drift over time, possibly due to gradual surface restructuring or poisoning effects [57,58].

In general, the voltage profiles demonstrate good stability across all conditions, with minimal degradation over the 14-hour period, highlighting the promise of Ag-coated carbon electrodes for sustained bicarbonate electrolysis. These findings underscore the critical role of deposition parameters in optimizing both initial activity and long-term stability of electrocatalysts for CO₂ reduction. While the 14-hour test demonstrates promising initial stability, extended durability evaluations, spanning over hundreds to thousands of hours, are essential to meet the requirements for industrial implementation. We emphasize that future work will focus on comprehensive long-term stability assessments and a systematic investigation of potential degradation mechanisms to ensure the practical viability of these electrodes for industrial applications.

Fig. 7. Stability test of Ag-coated 3D printed electrodes at different deposition potential and time. The zero-gap electrolytic flow cell was operated with 3 M KHCO₃ solution in a 2- electrode set-up. The measurements were done in galvanostatic mode applying a current density of 100 mA/cm². The data presented here include only measurements collected before the voltage exceeded a 10 % increase from the initial values.

3.6. Preliminary techno-economic insights

To assess the economic implication of bicarbonate electrolysis, a CO production cost estimation was deployed based on the current experimental data and typical material costs such as the catalyst. The contour plots in Fig. 8 reveal crucial insights into the cost optimization of CO production through bicarbonate electrolysis. At low catalyst loading (0.1 mg/cm^2) and -0.2 V deposition potential (Fig. 8a), the production costs exhibit a gradual increase with increasing current density in the range of 5.54 to $5.58 \text{ \$/kg CO}$. A more complex pattern emerges at -0.5 V (Fig. 8b), showing optimal cost regions around $40\text{--}60 \text{ mA/cm}^2$ with minimum costs of $5.59 \text{ \$/kg CO}$. The interplay between FE and cost demonstrates that moderate FE ranges ($6\text{--}11\%$ for 0.1 mg/cm^2 at -0.2 V , and $10\text{--}20\%$ at -0.5 V) yield the most economical operation. Notably, increasing the catalyst loading to 0.5 mg/cm^2 shifts the optimal FE window to $12\text{--}24\%$ for deposition potentials of -0.2 V (Fig. 8c) and $11\text{--}18\%$ for -0.5 V (Fig. 8d), resulting in production costs of $5.50\text{--}6 \text{ \$/kg CO}$. The deposition potential significantly influences the cost distribution, with -0.5 V showing a broader cost range ($5.60\text{--}6.50 \text{ \$/kg CO}$) compared to -0.2 V ($5.54\text{--}5.58 \text{ \$/kg CO}$) depending on the catalyst loading. The most economically favorable conditions were achieved with moderate catalyst loading (0.5 mg/cm^2), moderate to high current densities ($75\text{--}100 \text{ mA/cm}^2$) and FE of $6\text{--}13\%$ at -0.2 V deposition potential, yielding CO production costs as low as $5.54 \text{ \$/kg}$.

Overall, the trends indicate that higher FEs generally lead to lower CO production costs, but this relationship is modulated by current density and catalyst loading. Thus, our findings underscore the critical importance of interdependent optimization of operating parameters, such as catalyst loading, FE, and current density, to achieve cost-

effective CO production. Addressing these provides valuable insights for the rational design of industrial-scale bicarbonate electrolysis systems, with potential CO production costs competitive with conventional methods. It was highlighted that integrated CO_2 capture and electrochemical conversion can reduce energy consumption by up to 44% compared to sequential processes at high performances [65]. Moreover, a recent techno-economic analysis investigation by Kim *et al.* indicates that these systems can achieve a CO breakeven price below $\$1/\text{kg}$ under optimal conditions [66]. Future work should focus on optimizing catalyst and electrode configurations, as well as improving membrane designs, with particular emphasis on enhancing the stability of the bipolar MEA under industrial conditions. Challenges faced in closed-loop applications such as mismatched pH conditions, inefficient solvent regeneration, and impractical contactor sizing must be addressed for real-world implementation [67]. From a materials perspective, not only electrodes but also addressing challenges in BPM design is critical for the development of low-cost and high-performance bicarbonate electrolysis [68,69]. These efforts aim to address the trade-offs between material costs and operational efficiency, enabling the large-scale, cost-effective implementation of bicarbonate electrolysis.

4. Conclusion and outlook

This study introduces an innovative design for bicarbonate electrolysis using a BPM-3D-EA system that combines the efficiency of bipolar membranes with the structural and catalytic advantages of 3D-printed microlattice carbon electrodes coated with Ag nanoparticles. Among the sixteen designs tested, the optimal Ag-coated configuration exhibited a threefold increase in FE_{CO} compared to the uncoated

Fig. 8. Contour plots showing the variation in CO production cost during bicarbonate electrolysis as a function of FE for CO and current density, across different catalyst loadings and deposition potentials for optimized electrode configurations. For a low catalyst loading of 0.1 mg/cm^2 , deposition potentials of (a) $-0.2 \text{ V vs Ag/AgCl}$ and (b) $-0.5 \text{ V vs Ag/AgCl}$ were evaluated. For a higher catalyst loading of 0.5 mg/cm^2 , deposition potentials of (c) $-0.2 \text{ V vs Ag/AgCl}$ and (d) $-0.5 \text{ V vs Ag/AgCl}$ were investigated. The plots highlight the cost reduction trends and the impact of varying operating conditions on CO production efficiency.

counterpart, achieving up to 37.3 % and maintaining excellent stability over 14 h of continuous operation. With an ICPI of 150 mA/Vmg at 75 mA/cm², the configuration prepared at -0.2 V for 900 s with 0.5 mg/cm² Ag loading highlights the best effectiveness of tailoring Ag nanostructures on 3D-printed electrodes for enhanced catalytic activity in CO₂ reduction. A preliminary techno-economic analysis indicates that the cost of CO production using the BPM-3D-EA system could be significantly reduced through targeted optimization of critical operational parameters, such as FE and catalyst loading. When coupled with the system's modular and scalable design, these advancements underscore the potential of this technology as a competitive alternative to conventional CO₂ electrolysis methods. Despite the significant potential of integrating bipolar membranes with 3D-printed microlattice carbon electrodes to transform the scalability and economic feasibility of electrochemical CO₂ reduction technologies, further advancements are essential to bridge the gap toward industrial deployment. Specifically, refining the morphology of 3D-printed electrodes, optimizing the electrode-membrane interface, and controlling the morphology of electrodeposited Ag nanoparticles are critical to enhancing FE_{CO} at industrially relevant current densities while reducing overall energy consumption. Besides, while the Ag catalyst deposition across the internal surfaces of the 3D microlattice current is successfully demonstrated, further in-depth investigation is necessary to systematically optimize the uniformity, thickness, and morphology of the internal coatings. Moreover, overcoming mass transport limitations at higher current densities is crucial for enhancing selectivity and efficiency under practical operating conditions, as it ensures optimal reactant availability and minimizes competing reactions. Moreover, further morphological optimization of the 3D microlattice structure, along with detailed electrochemical characterization, including electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) and direct comparisons with conventional electrode morphologies, is essential to quantitatively validate the observed mass transport benefits and to elucidate the mechanisms by which the microlattice architecture mitigates concentration gradients during operation. Addressing long-term stability issues, such as catalyst degradation and agglomeration, as well as the efficiency and durability of the BPM remains vital for sustained performance. By mitigating the identified challenges and leveraging the flexibility of 3D printing, the BPM-3D-EA system could play a pivotal role in advancing carbon capture and utilization technologies, contributing to a more sustainable and circular carbon economy. Our study lays the groundwork for future advancements in electrochemical systems, and with continued efforts to enhance electrode design and operational stability, the BPM-3D-EA system could play a pivotal role in advancing sustainable carbon capture and utilization technologies.

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Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Supplementary materials

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Data availability

The data supporting this article have been included as part of the ESI.

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